

THE EFFECT OF BRAND IMAGE AND SERVICE QUALITY ON LOYALTY THROUGH PATIENT SATISFACTION AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE AT CLINIC A IN KUDUS CITY (Study at Clinic A in Kudus City, Central Java)

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Abstract

This study was conducted due to increasingly fierce competition in the healthcare industry and patients' low tendency to recommend, reuse, and make Clinic A in Kudus City their first choice. The aim was to obtain empirical evidence regarding the influence of brand image and service quality on patient loyalty through patient satisfaction as an intervening variable. The method used was descriptive verification analysis with a quantitative approach. Data were collected through questionnaires distributed to patients at Clinic A in Kudus City. The sample size was determined using Hair's formula, which is five to ten times the number of research indicators. Data analysis was performed using path analysis and the Sobel test to examine the mediating role. The results the analysis show that brand image, service quality, patient satisfaction, and patient loyalty are good. Partially and simultaneously, brand image and service quality have a positive and significant effect on patient satisfaction and loyalty. Patient satisfaction is also proven to mediate the effect of brand image and service quality on patient loyalty. Therefore, Clinic A in Kudus City is advised to continue to improve its brand image and service quality in order to strengthen patient satisfaction and loyalty on an ongoing basis.

Keywords: *brand image, service quality, patient satisfaction, and patient loyalty.*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of the healthcare industry has encouraged healthcare providers to continuously innovate and implement various strategies in order to remain competitive. Healthcare facilities such as independent medical practices, clinics, community health centers, hospitals, and other healthcare institutions play an essential role as the main actors in the healthcare service sector (Pratami et al., 2023). In recent years, health issues have become one of the major concerns of society. As people's living standards continue to improve, the demand for high-quality healthcare services is also increasing (Imran et al., 2021). According to the Indonesian Health Profile 2023, the number of hospitals in Indonesia has reached 3,155 units, consisting of 2,636 general hospitals and 519 specialized hospitals operated by both the government and private sectors (Sibuea & Hardhana, 2023). In an increasingly competitive healthcare environment, healthcare providers are required to continuously improve service quality in order to achieve patient satisfaction and maintain patient loyalty (Dam & Dam, 2021). Healthcare institutions must also maintain relationships with existing patients while simultaneously attracting potential patients to prevent them from switching to other healthcare providers (Apriliani, 2019). In this context, patient loyalty becomes an important factor for healthcare institutions because loyal patients are more likely to continue using healthcare services and recommend them to others (Paradilla et al., 2022).

Customer loyalty can be defined as a strong commitment to repurchase or continue using a preferred product or service consistently in the future (Kotler & Keller, 2020). In healthcare services, patient loyalty is reflected in patients' willingness to return to the same healthcare facility whenever they require medical treatment (Rinaldi, 2018). Loyalty is also characterized by patients' tendency to share positive experiences and recommend the healthcare provider to others (Dachi, 2020). Therefore, patient loyalty is considered a crucial factor in ensuring the sustainability and success of healthcare institutions (Lin & Yin, 2022). One of the healthcare facilities operating in Kudus City is Clinic A, which provides medical services to the surrounding community. However, preliminary observations indicate several problems experienced by patients, particularly long waiting times due to patient queues and delays in doctors' arrival schedules. These issues can disrupt the service process and potentially reduce patient satisfaction, which in turn may affect patient loyalty.

The results of a preliminary survey conducted among patients at Clinic A indicate that patient loyalty still needs to be improved. Many patients are hesitant to recommend the clinic to others and are reluctant to share positive experiences regarding the healthcare services provided. In addition, several patients do not consistently choose Clinic A as their primary healthcare provider and show a tendency to seek medical treatment at other clinics. These findings indicate that patient loyalty at Clinic A remains relatively low and requires further attention. One factor that may influence patient loyalty is brand image. Brand image refers to a set of beliefs and perceptions held by consumers regarding a particular brand (Kotler & Keller, 2020). A positive brand image can strengthen consumers' trust and emotional attachment toward a service provider (Sanggarwati & Laily, 2023). In healthcare services, brand image can influence patients' perceptions regarding service quality, reliability, and professionalism of the healthcare provider (Muin et al., 2024). A strong brand image may encourage patients to maintain long-term relationships with healthcare providers because they believe that the services offered are reliable and consistent (Aaker, 1991, as cited in Supangat et al., 2022).

Several previous studies have found that brand image has a positive and significant influence on customer loyalty (Trisno et al., 2023; Rindasiwi & Pattyranie, 2024). A positive brand image can increase customer trust and strengthen their intention to continue using the services provided (Daniswara & Rahardjo, 2023). However, the preliminary survey conducted at Clinic A shows that patients' perceptions of the clinic's brand image still need improvement. Some patients believe that the clinic has not fully met their expectations, while others find it difficult to understand the information provided by the clinic. These findings indicate that the current brand image of Clinic A may influence patients' willingness to continue using its services. Another important factor affecting patient loyalty is service quality. Service quality is defined as the level of excellence expected by customers and the ability of service providers to meet those expectations (Haryoko et al., 2020). In healthcare services, high service quality can create positive experiences for patients and lead to higher levels of satisfaction and loyalty (Winata et al., 2022). Patients generally expect healthcare providers to deliver services that meet their needs and expectations because healthcare services are closely related to their well-being (Afriani & Setyono, 2017).

Previous studies have shown that service quality has a positive influence on patient loyalty (Pasya, 2024; Andriani et al., 2023). High service quality can increase patient satisfaction and encourage patients to continue using the services of a particular healthcare provider (Actavinus & Purnomo, 2023). However, some studies have reported different findings. For example, research conducted by (Winata et al., 2022) found that service quality does not always have a direct effect on patient loyalty. These differences indicate that other factors may mediate the relationship between service quality and loyalty. One important factor that may mediate this relationship is patient satisfaction. Customer satisfaction refers to the emotional response that arises after customers compare their expectations with the actual performance of the service received (Kotler & Keller, 2020). When service performance meets or exceeds expectations, customers tend to feel satisfied. Conversely, when the performance falls below expectations, customers may experience dissatisfaction (Supangat et al., 2022).

Several studies suggest that brand image and service quality may influence customer loyalty indirectly through satisfaction as a mediating variable (Al Islamiyah & Wuisan, 2024; Osei et al., 2024). Patient satisfaction plays an important role in strengthening long-term relationships between patients and healthcare providers (Actavinus & Purnomo, 2023). However, previous studies have shown inconsistent findings. For example, (Paradilla et al., 2022) found that patient satisfaction does not always mediate the relationship between brand image and loyalty, indicating that the relationships among these variables are complex and require further investigation. Based on the preliminary survey conducted at Clinic A, patient satisfaction levels are also relatively low. Many respondents reported that the services provided did not exceed their expectations, waiting times were still considered long, and patient complaints were not always handled effectively. These findings highlight the need to improve service quality and strengthen the clinic's brand image in order to enhance patient satisfaction and

ultimately increase patient loyalty. Considering the phenomena and research gaps identified in previous studies, it is important to further examine the relationships among brand image, service quality, patient satisfaction, and patient loyalty in healthcare services. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the influence of brand image and service quality on patient loyalty through patient satisfaction as an intervening variable at Clinic A in Kudus City.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Loyalty

Customer loyalty can be defined as a form of deep emotional attachment and consistent commitment from customers toward a particular product, service, or brand. Loyalty is reflected in customer behavior that demonstrates a long-term commitment to continue using the same product or service even when various alternative options are available in the market. Loyal customers not only continue to use the service themselves but also voluntarily recommend the product or service to others, such as family members, friends, and colleagues (Wahyuni & Nainggolan, 2024). Loyalty does not emerge from spontaneous or temporary decisions but rather develops through an ongoing relationship between customers and service providers, which is built from repeated positive experiences and consistently maintained satisfaction. In this regard, (Najmudin & Dwiwinarno, 2020) explain that loyalty represents a commitment shown by customers to continue choosing and purchasing a particular product or brand in the future despite the existence of competing alternatives in the market.

In general, the concept of loyalty describes the level of strong attachment or emotional commitment that individuals have toward something, whether it is an individual, organization, group, or system of values. In the business context, particularly within service industries such as healthcare, customer loyalty plays a strategic role. (Sriani et al., 2019) explain that from a company's perspective, customer loyalty is a key component of effective service management. When customers are loyal to a particular service, they are less likely to switch to competitors even when attractive offers are presented. Loyalty reflects a strong commitment to continue using services from the same provider despite external influences or marketing efforts from competitors. Similarly, (Kotler et al., 2018) define loyalty as a deeply held commitment to repurchase or continue using a preferred product or service consistently in the future. Even under dynamic market conditions and promotional pressures from competitors, loyal customers tend to remain with the same provider. Such loyalty becomes a valuable asset for companies because it contributes to business stability and long-term profitability.

Furthermore, (Griffin et al., 2003, as cited in Soeharso & Wikantari, 2022) describe loyalty as a form of consumer behavior in the decision-making process where customers consistently choose to purchase products or use services from the same company repeatedly. In this context, customer loyalty is closely associated with brand loyalty. Brand loyalty does not arise instantly but is formed through continuous positive experiences and high levels of satisfaction with the services provided. When customers feel satisfied with a product or service, they develop a strong desire to maintain their relationship with the service provider. Loyal customers tend to have a long-term commitment to continue using the same brand even when many alternative choices are available in the market. They not only engage in repeat purchases but also demonstrate a tendency not to switch brands or service providers (Lisdiana et al., 2023).

In healthcare services, loyalty plays a particularly important role because loyal patients tend to continue choosing the same healthcare facility without being easily influenced by promotional offers from competitors. (Dachi, 2020) emphasizes that loyalty is not only reflected through repeated service usage but also through the willingness to recommend the service to others. In the healthcare context, (Al Rasyid, 2017) explains that patient loyalty can be measured through several indicators, including the intention to revisit the healthcare facility, the willingness to recommend the healthcare services to others, and the commitment toward the healthcare institution or service provider. Furthermore, a study conducted by (Dayan et al., 2022) adopted patient loyalty indicators developed by (Askariazad & Babakhani, 2015) to evaluate the level of loyalty in healthcare services. These indicators are designed to measure the loyal behavior demonstrated by patients toward hospital services. The indicators include:

1. Recommending the hospital services to others.
2. Using other healthcare services offered by the hospital.
3. Choosing the hospital as the first option when healthcare services are needed.

These indicators provide a clear framework for measuring patient loyalty in practice and can serve as a basis for healthcare institutions to improve service quality and strengthen patient relationships.

Patient Satisfaction

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In the provision of healthcare services, patient satisfaction is a crucial aspect that cannot be overlooked, as it plays a significant role in supporting the overall success of health promotion programs (Sitepu & Kosasih, 2024). Patient satisfaction is often used as a primary indicator in evaluating the quality of services provided by healthcare facilities. High-quality healthcare services are generally assessed based on the extent to which they are able to provide satisfaction to patients. In line with the definition proposed by (Halim, 2024), patient satisfaction refers to the result of an evaluation or assessment conducted after receiving a service, in which the service is perceived to have met or even exceeded patient expectations. Therefore, patient satisfaction becomes one of the main elements in the implementation of healthcare quality assurance systems. It is also considered a crucial dimension in assessing the overall quality of healthcare services. Essentially, patient satisfaction arises as a response when patients' needs and desires are fulfilled according to their prior expectations (Nurmiwiyati et al., 2020).

According to (Kotler et al., 2018), satisfaction is an emotional condition that appears in the form of feelings of pleasure or disappointment, depending on how individuals compare their expectations with the actual results obtained from a particular product or service. This definition is further clarified by (Oliver, 1981), who states that satisfaction is a complex psychological condition formed from a combination of emotions that arise due to discrepancies between expectations and reality, and is influenced by previous feelings based on an individual's consumption experience. (Anggaraeni, 2021) also adds that satisfaction is an emotional manifestation experienced by individuals, in this case patients, after comparing their experiences when receiving services with the quality of services they previously expected. Patient satisfaction arises as a reaction to the experiences they encounter while interacting with various aspects of healthcare services, including perceptions of service quality and expectations regarding the outcomes of the services received. In this perspective, satisfaction is considered a subjective evaluation because it strongly depends on how closely the patient's initial expectations align with the actual experience after receiving the service (Ferreira et al., 2023). Therefore, in the healthcare sector, patient satisfaction is often viewed as one of the final outcome indicators that reflects the extent to which the healthcare service system has successfully achieved its objectives. Moreover, patient satisfaction is also one of the main goals in continuous efforts to improve overall service quality (Andrianti & Marlina, 2022). Patient satisfaction can essentially be used as a measure of the level of satisfaction experienced by patients after receiving healthcare services, which is obtained by comparing perceived service performance with their prior expectations (Dahlan, 2020). Furthermore, according to (Lisdiana et al., 2023), patient satisfaction can be interpreted as an evaluation of the quality of products or services offered by hospitals or healthcare institutions. When patients feel that their expectations have been fulfilled, they are more likely to return and use the services of the same hospital in the future. This condition can indirectly create patient loyalty toward the hospital, which becomes an important asset in maintaining and increasing public trust in healthcare institutions.

(Santoso & Bernarto, 2022) state that patient satisfaction is an important indicator in healthcare services and is influenced by several factors. These factors include the availability of adequate supporting facilities and the quality of services provided by hospitals. The level of satisfaction generally emerges from the comparison between patient expectations before receiving services and the reality they experience after undergoing the service process. If the actual experience perceived by patients matches or even exceeds their expectations, it will generate a feeling of satisfaction. Conversely, when there is a gap between expectations and the reality experienced, the level of satisfaction will decrease and may lead to disappointment. The feelings of satisfaction or dissatisfaction experienced by patients are closely related to their perceptions of the service outcomes provided. When patients feel satisfied, it indicates that healthcare facilities have successfully met or exceeded their expectations. However, if satisfaction is not achieved, it suggests that there are weaknesses in the services that need to be reviewed and improved (Novaryatiin et al., 2018). Therefore, patient satisfaction not only reflects perceptions of healthcare services but also serves as an important measurement tool used by hospitals and other healthcare facilities to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of services provided to the community.

To assess the level of patient satisfaction more objectively, (Kotler et al., 2018) identify several key indicators that can be used to measure consumer satisfaction toward services, including healthcare services. These indicators include:

1. Receiving adequate services.
2. Completing tasks efficiently and promptly.
3. Professional staff possessing sufficient knowledge and skills.
4. Being responsive to patient complaints.

These four indicators represent dimensions of service quality that directly influence the level of satisfaction experienced by patients.

Brand Image

According to (Kotler & Keller, 2018), brand image can be understood as the perception or impression formed in an individual's mind regarding a particular brand. This perception arises from both direct and indirect experiences that individuals have with the brand, which ultimately creates a specific image in their minds. Meanwhile, (Afriani & Setyono, 2017) define brand image as the result of associations embedded in consumers' memories when they recall a particular brand. These associations may take the form of thoughts, ideas, or perceptions connected to the brand. Brand image is formed through a series of consumer experiences that may generate either positive or negative feelings toward the brand, which are then stored in consumers' memory. When the image formed tends to be negative, the likelihood that consumers will choose or use the brand becomes lower (Yunaida, 2017).

(Arianty & Andira, 2021) state that brand image represents the overall picture derived from the associations and beliefs held by consumers toward a brand. In other words, brand image is the result of consumers' observational processes that involve perceptions and beliefs they build and trust regarding a particular brand. According to (Keller, 2013), as cited in (Pandiangan et al., 2021), several key dimensions constitute brand image, namely:

1. Brand Identity

Brand identity refers to the visual or physical elements of a brand, such as logos, colors, packaging shapes, and slogans, which function to create a strong identity that is easily recognized by consumers.

2. Brand Personality

Brand personality refers to the distinctive characteristics or traits associated with a brand that resemble human personality traits, such as warmth, firmness, creativity, or friendliness, which differentiate the brand from its competitors.

3. Brand Association

Brand association refers to any form of element or symbol consistently linked by consumers with a particular brand, including product uniqueness, social activities, public figures, or specific meanings strongly attached to the brand.

4. Brand Attitude and Behavior

Brand attitude and behavior represent the way a brand interacts with consumers, including the values offered, the manner in which brand messages are communicated, and the behavior of employees when delivering services to customers.

5. Brand Benefit and Competence

Brand benefit and competence refer to the benefits and unique advantages of a brand that are capable of fulfilling customers' needs, desires, and even aspirations through the values it provides.

Furthermore, (Keller, 2013) as cited in (Adiwidjaja & Tarigan, 2017) identifies several indicators used to measure brand image more specifically. These indicators include:

1. Favorability of Brand Associations

This indicator reflects the extent to which consumers hold positive views toward a brand because it is perceived to provide benefits that are relevant to their needs.

- a. Desirable, the brand is perceived as capable of fulfilling customers' expectations and desires.

- b. Deliverable, information and benefits of the brand can be communicated clearly and effectively to consumers.

2. Strength of Brand Associations

This indicator describes the strength of brand associations based on the quality and consistency of information embedded in consumers' memories, as well as how strongly the brand image is maintained.

- a. Personal Relevance, the higher the consumer's attachment to the brand due to previous experiences, the easier it is for the brand image to be formed.

- b. Consistency, consistent brand messaging makes it easier for consumers to recognize and trust the brand.

3. Uniqueness of Brand Associations

This indicator shows how unique a brand is in the minds of consumers, which distinguishes it from competing brands and provides a particular attraction.

- a. Point of Difference, unique associations offered by the brand are considered valuable and can be evaluated more positively by consumers compared to associations attached to other brands

Service Quality

According to (Kotler & Keller, 2018), service quality can be defined as the overall features, characteristics, and attributes inherent in a product or service that determine its ability to satisfy consumer needs, either directly or indirectly. In the context of healthcare services, this aspect becomes particularly crucial because healthcare is one of the fundamental needs that must be fulfilled in order for individuals to maintain a balanced and healthy life. Healthcare services do not only involve medical aspects but also concern how the services are delivered by adhering to established quality standards. In line with this perspective, (Novaryatiin et al., 2018) explain that service quality in the healthcare sector reflects services designed in such a way as to create patient satisfaction. Good services must be provided in accordance with standard operating procedures (SOPs) and professional ethical codes in order to meet public expectations of professional and ethical healthcare services. Service quality reflects the extent to which the services provided are able to meet patient expectations and needs. An organization can be considered successful in providing products or services when the services align with patients' desires and expectations (Halim, 2024). Furthermore, (Sari & Suryani, 2023) state that service quality can also be viewed as a benchmark for evaluating how well the services provided meet or even exceed customer expectations. Based on this perspective, (Ariany, 2021) defines service quality as a series of actions or activities carried out by one party for another in order to fulfill both physical and emotional needs.

In the modern era, which is characterized by increasingly intense industrial competition, particularly in the healthcare sector, every healthcare facility is required to continuously innovate and maintain consistency in delivering services that create sustainable patient satisfaction (Faeni, 2023). It is not sufficient for healthcare facilities to merely provide high-quality services; they must also consider the cost or affordability of services so that they remain accessible to the public. According to (Suryadana, 2017), in order to grow and remain competitive, hospitals and clinics must create an ideal balance between the value of services provided and the level of patient satisfaction achieved. This means that the services offered must not only be of high quality but also provide benefits that are proportional to the costs incurred by patients. Achieving this balance becomes an essential factor in building patient loyalty and ensuring the long-term sustainability of healthcare facilities. Furthermore, (Kotler & Keller, 2018) explain that in evaluating and measuring service quality, there are five main dimensions that can be used as a framework to assess various aspects of services that influence customer perceptions. These five dimensions provide a comprehensive and holistic view of how services are experienced by customers. The dimensions are described as follows (Halim, 2024):

1. Reliability

Reliability refers to the ability of an organization to deliver services accurately, consistently, and on time according to promises made to customers. It also includes the ability of employees to perform their duties professionally and meet customer expectations, thereby building trust in the service provider.

2. Responsiveness

Responsiveness refers to the willingness and readiness of staff to assist customers and provide prompt services. This includes providing clear and accurate information, such as service waiting times, and the ability to adjust services according to the specific needs or preferences of customers.

3. Assurance

Assurance reflects the level of trust and confidence customers have in the professionalism, competence, and integrity of service providers. This dimension is demonstrated through employees' attitudes and behaviors that create a sense of security and comfort for customers.

4. Empathy

Empathy reflects the organization's ability to provide individualized attention and understanding toward customers. This dimension includes warm and open communication, the ability to understand customer problems, and the willingness to act in accordance with their needs and interests. Empathy plays a crucial role in building positive emotional relationships between customers and service providers.

5. Tangibles

Tangibles refer to all physical aspects that can be directly observed by customers, such as the condition of facilities, the completeness of equipment, environmental cleanliness, and the neat and professional appearance of staff. These tangible aspects create strong first impressions and play an important role in shaping perceptions of overall service quality.

METHOD

This study employed a quantitative research approach using a descriptive and causal analysis design. The descriptive method was applied to describe the characteristics of the data obtained from respondents as they are, without manipulating the actual conditions, thereby allowing the researcher to draw general conclusions from the collected data. Descriptive research is intended to systematically describe specific phenomena based on empirical observations (Halim, 2025). In addition to the descriptive approach, this study also applied a causal analysis approach aimed at examining the influence between variables and testing the hypotheses formulated prior to data collection. Quantitative research is grounded in the positivist paradigm, which emphasizes the importance of empirical data in testing predetermined hypotheses (Sugiyono, 2019). This approach focuses on objective measurement of variables through the collection and statistical analysis of numerical data. Therefore, the study emphasizes systematic procedures, objectivity, and the identification of causal relationships among variables (Halim, 2025).

The population of this study consisted of patients who visited Clinic A. However, the exact number of patients could not be determined with certainty because the number of visitors to the clinic is dynamic and continuously changes over time. In situations where the population size cannot be clearly identified, sampling techniques are commonly used to obtain representative data from a portion of the population. A sample refers to a subset of the population that possesses specific characteristics and is considered capable of representing the entire population (Asrulla et al., 2023). The sample size in this study was determined using the guideline proposed by Hair et al. (2019), which suggests that the ideal number of respondents in multivariate analysis should be between five and ten times the number of indicators used in the research instrument. Since this study employed 15 measurement indicators, the minimum required sample size was 75 respondents (15×5), while the maximum recommended size was 150 respondents (15×10). This guideline ensures that the statistical analysis performed in the study has sufficient validity and reliability.

The sampling technique used in this research was purposive sampling, which is classified as a non-probability sampling method. In non-probability sampling, not all members of the population have the same opportunity to be selected as research participants (Septianie et al., 2020). Purposive sampling involves selecting respondents based on specific criteria that are considered relevant to the objectives of the research. According to Halim (2025), this technique allows researchers to focus on individuals who are believed to possess the necessary experience or characteristics required to provide accurate and relevant information. In this study, the respondents were selected based on the criterion that they had visited the clinic at least twice within the last three months. This criterion was applied to ensure that respondents had sufficient experience with the clinic's services and were therefore capable of providing informed evaluations regarding service quality, brand image, patient satisfaction, and loyalty.

Data used in this research were collected in the form of numerical values that could be processed and analyzed using statistical techniques. The primary data collection method involved the distribution of structured questionnaires to the selected respondents. The questionnaire contained a series of statements related to the research variables, and respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with each statement based on their experiences with the clinic's services. The responses were measured using a Likert scale, which allows the researcher to quantify respondents' perceptions and attitudes toward the studied variables. The use of structured questionnaires facilitates systematic data collection and enables quantitative analysis of the relationships among variables. This study utilized two main types of data sources, namely primary data and secondary data. Primary data were obtained directly from respondents through the questionnaire survey conducted during the research process. These data were specifically collected to address the research questions and test the proposed hypotheses. Secondary data, on the other hand, were gathered from various supporting sources such as academic journals, previous research findings, textbooks, and other relevant publications. Secondary data play an important role in strengthening the theoretical foundation of the study and providing additional insights that support the interpretation of the research findings (Sugiyono, 2017). The combination of primary and secondary data in this research helps ensure that the analysis is both empirically grounded and theoretically supported.

THE EFFECT OF BRAND IMAGE AND SERVICE QUALITY ON LOYALTY THROUGH PATIENT SATISFACTION AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE AT CLINIC A IN KUDUS CITY

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity

Table 1. Validity Test Result

Uji Validitas					
Brand Image					
Item	Pearson Correlation	Rtabel	Sig. (2-tailed)	Alpha	Description
BI_1	.888**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
BI_2	.877**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
BI_3	.929**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
BI_4	.851**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
BI_5	.857**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
BI_6	.778**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
Service Quality					
Item	Pearson Correlation	Rtabel	Sig. (2-tailed)	Alpha	Description
KL_1	.909**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KL_2	.833**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KL_3	.923**	0.1966	0.020	0.05	Valid
KL_4	.939**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KL_5	.863**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KL_6	.769**	0.1966	0.001	0.05	Valid
KL_7	.863**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KL_8	.894**	0.1966	0.006	0.05	Valid
KL_9	.849**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KL_10	.938**	0.1966	0.009	0.05	Valid
Patient Satisfaction					
Item	Pearson Correlation	Rtabel	Sig. (2-tailed)	Alpha	Description
KP_1	.933**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KP_2	.940**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KP_3	.850**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KP_4	.779**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KP_5	.940**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KP_6	.975**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KP_7	.888**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
KP_8	.975**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
Loyalty					
Item	Pearson Correlation	Rtabel	Sig. (2-tailed)	Alpha	Description
L_1	.900**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
L_2	.774**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
L_3	.903**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
L_4	.884**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
L_5	.929**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid
L_6	.770**	0.1966	0.000	0.05	Valid

Based on Table 1, all questionnaire items used in this study are declared valid. This conclusion is drawn because the Pearson correlation values for each item are greater than the r-table value (0.1966), and all significance values are below the threshold of 0.05. These results indicate that all indicators measuring the variables of brand image, service quality, patient satisfaction, and loyalty are able to accurately measure the intended constructs and are therefore suitable for further analysis.

Reliability Test

Table 2. Reliability Test Result

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items	Description
Brand Image	0.932	6	Reliable
Service Quality	0.967	10	Reliable
Patient Satisfaction	0.970	8	Reliable
Loyalty	0.930	6	Reliable

Based on the reliability test results conducted for all research variables, it is found that each variable has a Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.90. This indicates that all questionnaire items have very strong internal consistency. The brand image variable obtained a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.932 with six items, indicating that the instrument is highly reliable. The service quality variable achieved a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.967 with ten items, which shows a very high level of reliability. Furthermore, the patient satisfaction variable also demonstrates excellent reliability with a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.970 from eight items. Lastly, the loyalty variable obtained a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.930 with six items, indicating that the instrument used to measure this variable is also highly reliable. Overall, these results demonstrate that all research instruments have very high reliability and are therefore suitable for further analysis.

Normality Test

Table 3. Normality Test Results

Model	Sig.	Sign	Alpha	Description
Regression 1	0.200	>	0.05	Normally Distributed
Regression 2	0.200	>	0.05	Normally Distributed

Based on the normality test results presented in Table 3, it can be concluded that both regression models meet the normality assumption. This is indicated by the significance values (Sig.) of 0.200 for both Regression 1 and Regression 2, which are greater than the alpha level of 0.05. These results show that the data are normally distributed and suitable for further regression analysis.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 4. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Model	Variable	Sig.	Sign	Alpha	Description
Regression 1 (Loyalty)	Brand Image	0.813	>	0.05	No Heteroscedasticity Problem
	Service Quality	0.649	>	0.05	No Heteroscedasticity Problem
	Patient Satisfaction	0.205	>	0.05	No Heteroscedasticity Problem
Regression 2 (Patient Satisfaction)	Brand Image	0.105	>	0.05	No Heteroscedasticity Problem
	Service Quality	0.529	>	0.05	No Heteroscedasticity Problem

Based on the heteroscedasticity test results shown in Table 4, it can be concluded that both regression models do not experience heteroscedasticity problems. This is indicated by the significance values (Sig.) of all independent variables in both models being greater than the alpha level of 0.05. In Regression 1 (Loyalty), the variables Brand Image (0.813), Service Quality (0.649), and Patient Satisfaction (0.205) show no heteroscedasticity issues. Similarly, in Regression 2 (Patient Satisfaction), the variables Brand Image (0.105) and Service Quality (0.529) also meet the homoscedasticity assumption. Therefore, the regression models used in this study satisfy the classical assumption with stable residual variance.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Variable	Tolerance	Limit	VIF	Limit	Description
Regression 1	Brand Image	0.613	≥ 0.10	1.631	≤ 10.00	No Multicollinearity
	Service Quality	0.638	≥ 0.10	1.567	≤ 10.00	No Multicollinearity
	Patient Satisfaction	0.428	≥ 0.10	2.336	≤ 10.00	No Multicollinearity
Regression 2	Brand Image	0.962	≥ 0.10	1.040	≤ 10.00	No Multicollinearity
	Service Quality	0.962	≥ 0.10	1.040	≤ 10.00	No Multicollinearity

Based on the multicollinearity test results shown in Table 5, it can be concluded that both regression models are free from multicollinearity problems. This is indicated by the tolerance values of all variables being greater than the threshold of 0.10 and the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) values being lower than the limit of 10.00. In Regression 1, the variables Brand Image, Service Quality, and Patient Satisfaction have tolerance values of 0.613, 0.638, and 0.428 respectively, with VIF values below 2.336. In Regression 2, both independent variables also meet the criteria with tolerance values of 0.962 and VIF values of 1.040. Therefore, there is no strong correlation among the independent variables in this research model.

Path Analysis

Path analysis is used to examine causal relationships between variables, including direct and indirect effects through mediating variables (Keneq, 2020). In this study, this method was applied to analyze the influence of independent variables (brand image and service quality) on patient loyalty with patient satisfaction as the mediating variable.

Table 6. Direct and Indirect Effects of Research Variables

No	Description	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect
1	Effect of Brand Image on Patient Satisfaction ($X_1 \rightarrow Z$)	0.503 = 50.3%	–
2	Effect of Service Quality on Patient Satisfaction ($X_2 \rightarrow Z$)	0.475 = 47.5%	–
3	Effect of Brand Image on Loyalty ($X_1 \rightarrow Y$)	0.279 = 27.9%	–
4	Effect of Service Quality on Loyalty ($X_2 \rightarrow Y$)	0.318 = 31.8%	–
5	Effect of Patient Satisfaction on Loyalty ($Z \rightarrow Y$)	0.341 = 34.1%	–
6	Effect of Brand Image on Loyalty through Patient Satisfaction ($X_1 \rightarrow Z \rightarrow Y$)	–	$0.503 \times 0.341 = 0.172 = 17.2\%$
7	Effect of Service Quality on Loyalty through Patient Satisfaction ($X_2 \rightarrow Z \rightarrow Y$)	–	$0.475 \times 0.341 = 0.162 = 16.2\%$

Based on the results of the direct and indirect effect analysis presented in Table 6, the findings show that brand image has a positive and relatively strong direct effect on patient satisfaction with a coefficient value of 0.503 or 50.3%. This indicates that the better the patient’s perception of the healthcare institution’s brand image, the higher the level of patient satisfaction. Service quality also has a positive direct effect on patient satisfaction with a coefficient value of 0.475 or 47.5%, which shows that improvements in service quality significantly contribute to increasing patient satisfaction. Furthermore, brand image has a positive direct effect on patient loyalty with a coefficient of 0.279 or 27.9%, indicating that a strong and positive brand image can encourage patients to remain loyal to the healthcare services they use. Service quality also directly affects patient loyalty with a coefficient value of 0.318 or 31.8%, meaning that patients tend to demonstrate higher loyalty when they perceive the service quality to be good and consistent. Patient satisfaction itself has a positive direct effect on patient loyalty with a coefficient value of 0.341 or 34.1%, confirming that satisfied patients are more likely to revisit and recommend the healthcare services to others. In addition to the direct effects, there are also indirect effects through patient satisfaction. Brand image has an indirect effect on patient loyalty through patient satisfaction with a value

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of 0.172 or 17.2%, indicating that patient satisfaction acts as a mediating variable that strengthens the relationship between brand image and loyalty. Likewise, service quality also has an indirect effect on patient loyalty through patient satisfaction with a coefficient value of 0.162 or 16.2%. This finding shows that improvements in service quality increase patient satisfaction, which subsequently leads to higher patient loyalty, confirming the mediating role of patient satisfaction in the relationship between service quality and patient loyalty.

First Hypothesis Test

Table 6. Hypothesis Test Result I

Model		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		Beta	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.453	2.283	-0.636	0.526
	BrandImage	0.329	0.101	0.279	3.261
	Service Quality	0.290	0.076	0.318	3.795
	Patient Satisfaction	0.244	0.073	0.341	3.333

a. Dependent Variable: Loyalty

Based on the results of data processing presented in the recap of Hypothesis 1 analysis, the regression equation can be formulated as follows:

$$Y = -1.453 + 0.329X_1 + 0.290X_2 + 0.244X_3$$

The regression equation above can be explained as follows:

- a. Constant value of -1.453.
This means that if the variables Brand Image (X₁), Service Quality (X₂), and Patient Satisfaction (X₃) are equal to 0, then Loyalty (Y) has a value of 1.453. The negative constant indicates that without the contribution of these three variables, the level of loyalty tends to be at a relatively low level.
- b. Regression coefficient of Brand Image (X₁) of 0.329.
This means that if the other independent variables are assumed to remain constant and Brand Image (X₁) increases by one unit, then Loyalty (Y) will increase by 0.329. The positive coefficient indicates a positive relationship between Brand Image and Loyalty, meaning that the better the brand image, the higher the level of patient loyalty.
- c. Regression coefficient of Service Quality (X₂) of 0.290.
This means that if the other independent variables are assumed to remain constant and Service Quality (X₂) increases by one unit, then Loyalty (Y) will increase by 0.290. The positive coefficient indicates that higher service quality will lead to higher patient loyalty.
- d. Regression coefficient of Patient Satisfaction (X₃) of 0.244.
This means that if the other independent variables are assumed to remain constant and Patient Satisfaction (X₃) increases by one unit, then Loyalty (Y) will increase by 0.244. The positive coefficient indicates that the higher the level of patient satisfaction, the higher the loyalty formed.

Second Hypothesis Test

Table 7. Hypothesis Test Result 2

Model		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		Beta	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-6.741	3.087	-2.184	0.031
	BrandImage	0.828	0.111	0.503	7.425
	Service Quality	0.604	0.086	0.475	7.009

a. Dependent Variable: Patient Satisfaction

Based on the results of the partial test (t-test) presented in the Hypothesis 2 table, the following interpretations can be drawn regarding the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable, Patient Satisfaction.

1. The Brand Image variable has a significance value of 0.000, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$, and a positive regression coefficient (0.828). This indicates that Brand Image partially has a positive and

significant effect on Patient Satisfaction. Thus, it can be concluded that an improvement in the perception of Brand Image will significantly increase Patient Satisfaction.

- The Service Quality variable has a significance value of 0.000, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$, and a positive regression coefficient (0.604). This shows that Service Quality partially has a positive and significant effect on Patient Satisfaction. This means that improvements in Service Quality significantly contribute to increasing Patient Satisfaction.

Coefficient of Determination Analysis

Table 8. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Model	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square
X ₁ and X ₂ → Z	0.572	0.563
X ₁ , X ₂ , and Z → Y	0.569	0.555

Figure 1 illustrates the path analysis model that describes the causal relationships among HMIS (X), Based on the coefficient of determination results, it can be concluded that both regression models have moderate and consistent explanatory power. The R-Square value of 0.572 in the model X₁ and X₂ → Z indicates that the independent variables Brand Image and Service Quality are able to explain 57.2% of the variation in the dependent variable Patient Satisfaction, while the Adjusted R-Square value of 0.563 confirms the adequacy of the model after adjusting for the number of variables used. In the second model, X₁, X₂, and Z → Y, the R-Square value of 0.569 indicates that 56.9% of the variation in Patient Loyalty can be explained by Brand Image, Service Quality, and Patient Satisfaction, while the Adjusted R-Square value of 0.555 shows that the regression model remains stable after adjustment. Therefore, it can be concluded that the regression models used in this study are adequate in explaining the relationships among the research variables.

Sobel Test

- To what extent does Patient Satisfaction mediate the effect of Brand Image on Patient Loyalty at Clinic A in Kudus City?

Input:	Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a 0.828	Sobel test: 3.05024937	0.06623458	0.00228651
b 0.244	Aroian test: 3.02767656	0.0667284	0.00246442
s _a 0.111	Goodman test: 3.0733347	0.06573706	0.00211681
s _b 0.073	Reset all	Calculate	

Figure 1. Sobel Test

Based on the Sobel test results, it can be concluded that Patient Satisfaction significantly mediates the effect of Brand Image on Patient Loyalty at Clinic A in Kudus City. This is indicated by the Sobel test statistic value of 3.050 with a p-value of 0.002, which is much smaller than the significance level of 0.05. These results are also consistent with the Aroian test (p-value = 0.002) and the Goodman test (p-value = 0.002). Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant indirect effect in which Brand Image can increase Patient Loyalty through the improvement of Patient Satisfaction as a mediating variable.

- Hypothesis 7: To what extent does Patient Satisfaction mediate the effect of Service Quality on Patient Loyalty at Clinic A in Kudus City?

Input:	Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a 0.604	Sobel test: 3.01810419	0.04883065	0.00254361
b 0.244	Aroian test: 2.99346547	0.04923257	0.00275829
s _a 0.086	Goodman test: 3.0433615	0.0484254	0.00233951
s _b 0.073	Reset all	Calculate	

Figure 2. Sobel Test

Based on the Sobel test results, it can be concluded that Patient Satisfaction significantly mediates the effect of Service Quality on Patient Loyalty at Clinic A in Kudus City. This is proven by the Sobel test statistic value of 3.018 with a p-value of 0.002, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. Consistent results are also shown by the Aroian test (p-value = 0.002) and the Goodman test (p-value = 0.002). Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant indirect effect in which improvements in Service Quality can increase Patient Loyalty through increased Patient Satisfaction as the mediating variable.

Effect of Brand Image on Patient Satisfaction

The results of the analysis show that the coefficient of the effect of brand image on patient satisfaction is 0.503 or 50.3% with a significance value of 0.000 (< 0.05). The analysis also indicates that the brand image variable has a significance value of 0.000, which is below the error tolerance limit of $\alpha = 0.05$. This condition confirms that brand image has a positive and significant effect on patient satisfaction at Clinic A in Kudus City. This means that the better the patients' perception of the clinic's brand image, the higher the level of satisfaction experienced. The positive regression coefficient (0.828) indicates that the stronger the brand image of a clinic, the higher the level of satisfaction perceived by patients. These findings demonstrate that a strong brand image can build positive perceptions, trust, and confidence among patients regarding the quality of services provided, which ultimately leads to increased satisfaction. The results of this study are consistent with the research of Diputra & Yasa (2021), which states that brand image and brand trust have a positive and significant effect on satisfaction. The study by Mohammed & Rashid (2018) also supports these findings, where brand image was proven to have a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction. Thus, Hypothesis 1 (H1) stating that brand image affects patient satisfaction is accepted.

These findings illustrate that brand image is capable of building trust, where trust is an important factor contributing to service quality and customer satisfaction (Kundu & Datta, 2018). In the healthcare context, Dewi & Sukei (2022) state that brand image reflected in community popularity, credibility of healthcare institutions, competitive advantages over other facilities, and competitive service costs significantly influence patient loyalty by improving perceptions of service quality and satisfaction. Similarly, Hoşgör & Sevim (2022) found a positive relationship between brand image and patient satisfaction in hospitals. Brand image encompasses several elements such as service quality, credibility, uniqueness, and relevance associated with the clinic. When these elements are perceived positively by patients, they tend to experience more satisfying and convincing healthcare services (Ramadhana et al., 2025). Research by Alfiannor (2024) also indicates that brand image partially influences patient satisfaction in hospitals. Overall, the findings of this study confirm that brand image plays a significant role in increasing patient satisfaction, which aligns with hospital management principles that emphasize institutional reputation as a strategic element in the sustainability of healthcare services. From the perspective of hospital management, a strong brand image is an intangible asset that functions as a differentiation tool, increases public trust, and strengthens the relationship between patients and healthcare providers. By building a positive brand image through quality services, consistent communication, and professional operational standards, healthcare institutions can strengthen competitiveness and continuously improve patient satisfaction.

Effect of Service Quality on Patient Satisfaction

The test results show that service quality has a coefficient of 0.475 or 47.5% with a significance value of 0.000 (< 0.05). This indicates that service quality has a positive and significant effect on patient satisfaction at Clinic A in Kudus City. The positive regression coefficient (0.604) reinforces this finding, indicating that the better the service quality provided, the higher the level of patient satisfaction. Improvements in service quality, including reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangible aspects, significantly increase patient satisfaction. These findings are consistent with the study by Kosasih & Paramarta (2020) which states that improvements in healthcare service quality significantly contribute to increased patient satisfaction. Likewise, Diputra & Yasa (2021) found that product quality has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction. Research by Novitasari et al. (2022) also indicates a relationship between service quality and patient satisfaction. According to Almomani et al. (2020), this result aligns with the service quality concept, which emphasizes that customer satisfaction is strongly influenced by perceptions of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangible evidence provided by service providers. Patient satisfaction plays an important role in influencing various aspects of healthcare organizations because patient loyalty is highly influenced by perceived service quality. When patients feel satisfied, they develop positive opinions and feel comfortable with the services provided (Adelia & Purnama, 2025). Higher

service quality encourages long-term relationships between patients and healthcare providers and may even attract new patients (Zaid et al., 2022). Overall, the findings confirm that service quality significantly influences patient satisfaction, which aligns with the patient-centered care approach in hospital management. This approach emphasizes that every aspect of service, including medical staff competence, responsiveness, clear communication, and facility comfort, directly shapes patient satisfaction.

Effect of Brand Image on Patient Loyalty

The regression analysis results show that brand image has a coefficient of 0.279 or 27.9% with a significance value of 0.002 (< 0.05). This indicates that brand image has a positive and significant effect on patient loyalty. The positive coefficient shows that a strong brand image encourages patients to remain loyal to healthcare services. This finding is supported by Sanggarwati & Laily (2023), who found that brand image significantly influences consumer loyalty. Similarly, Hussain et al. (2025) stated that patients with positive perceptions of brand image tend to have higher trust and willingness to revisit the same healthcare service. According to Kotler & Keller (2016), a strong brand image creates emotional bonds and increases customer preference. Research by Rahmawati (2020) also shows that positive brand image increases customer loyalty through perceptions of quality and trust. Overall, these findings confirm that brand image plays a strategic role in building patient loyalty, aligning with hospital management principles emphasizing reputation, trust, and patient experience as key elements of healthcare sustainability.

Effect of Service Quality on Patient Loyalty

The results indicate that service quality has a positive and significant effect on patient loyalty with a coefficient of 0.318 or 31.8% and significance value 0.000 (< 0.05). This finding indicates that the better the service quality provided, the higher the patient loyalty. This result is consistent with SERVQUAL theory proposed by Parasuraman, which states that service quality is a key determinant of customer satisfaction and loyalty (Kosasih & Paramarta, 2020). Higher service quality creates positive experiences for patients, including convenient appointment scheduling, friendly staff, and comfortable clinical environments (Chishti et al., 2023). Improved service quality significantly increases patient retention (Paradilla et al., 2022). Thus, improving service quality becomes a strategic factor for clinics in maintaining patient loyalty.

Effect of Patient Satisfaction on Patient Loyalty

The analysis results show that patient satisfaction has a coefficient of 0.341 or 34.1% with a significance value of 0.001 (< 0.05). This indicates that patient satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on patient loyalty. Satisfied patients are more likely to revisit healthcare services and recommend them to others (Aribowo et al., 2024). Research by Lisdiana et al. (2023) also confirms that patient satisfaction is a key determinant of loyalty in healthcare services. Therefore, patient satisfaction not only represents the outcome of effective service delivery but also serves as a strategic asset supporting the sustainability and growth of healthcare institutions.

Patient Satisfaction Mediates the Effect of Brand Image on Loyalty

Path analysis results show that patient satisfaction significantly mediates the relationship between brand image and patient loyalty with an indirect effect of 0.172 (17.2%). The Sobel test result shows a statistic value of 3.050 with p-value 0.002 (< 0.05). These results indicate that brand image influences loyalty both directly and indirectly through patient satisfaction. This finding supports the brand equity theory, which states that strong brand perception increases customer satisfaction and loyalty (Diputra & Yasa, 2021).

Patient Satisfaction Mediates the Effect of Service Quality on Loyalty

The path analysis results show that service quality has an indirect effect on patient loyalty through patient satisfaction with a coefficient of 0.162 (16.2%). The Sobel test result indicates a statistic value of 3.018 with p-value 0.002 (< 0.05). This finding confirms that patient satisfaction acts as an intervening variable that strengthens the relationship between service quality and loyalty. Thus, improving service quality will have a greater impact when it also enhances patient satisfaction, which ultimately leads to stronger patient loyalty and institutional competitiveness in healthcare services.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study examining the influence of Brand Image and Service Quality on Patient Loyalty with Patient Satisfaction as a mediating variable at Clinic A in Kudus City, several conclusions can be drawn. The findings show that brand image has a positive and significant effect on patient satisfaction. This indicates that the better the brand image perceived by patients, the higher the level of satisfaction they experience. A positive brand image is able to build trust, strengthen patients' perceptions of service quality, and create confidence in the healthcare services provided by the clinic. The study also reveals that service quality has a positive and significant effect on patient satisfaction. Improvements in service quality, including aspects such as reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangible facilities, contribute significantly to increasing patient satisfaction. When patients perceive that the services provided meet or exceed their expectations, they tend to feel more satisfied with the healthcare experience. Furthermore, brand image is found to have a positive and significant influence on patient loyalty. A strong and positive brand image encourages patients to maintain their trust in the clinic and increases their willingness to continue using its services. This indicates that patients who perceive the clinic as reputable and reliable are more likely to remain loyal and revisit the facility in the future. Service quality is also proven to have a positive and significant effect on patient loyalty. High-quality healthcare services create positive patient experiences, which in turn strengthen patients' commitment to continue using the clinic's services. Patients who experience professional, responsive, and comfortable healthcare services are more likely to return for future treatments and recommend the clinic to others. In addition, patient satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on patient loyalty. Satisfied patients tend to develop stronger emotional connections with healthcare providers, leading to repeat visits and long-term relationships with the clinic. This confirms that satisfaction plays a crucial role in shaping loyal patient behavior.

The results of the mediation analysis further indicate that patient satisfaction significantly mediates the relationship between brand image and patient loyalty. This means that brand image not only directly affects loyalty but also indirectly influences loyalty by increasing patient satisfaction. When a positive brand image is supported by satisfying healthcare experiences, patients are more likely to develop long-term loyalty toward the clinic. Similarly, patient satisfaction also mediates the relationship between service quality and patient loyalty. Improvements in service quality first enhance patient satisfaction, which subsequently strengthens patient loyalty. This finding highlights that satisfaction serves as an important mechanism through which service quality influences patient loyalty. Overall, this study concludes that brand image and service quality play essential roles in improving patient satisfaction and loyalty. Patient satisfaction acts as a key mediating variable that strengthens the relationship between these factors and patient loyalty. Therefore, maintaining a positive brand image while continuously improving service quality is crucial for healthcare institutions to enhance patient satisfaction and sustain long-term patient loyalty.

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